

The experience of teaching mathematics in a multilingual classroom: The case of a bilingual teacher

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This study seeks to unfold the factors that contribute to the teaching experience of a bilingual mathematics teacher in multilingual classrooms in the British educational system in two countries, the United Kingdom and Greece. The data produced by the narratives of a case study were analysed following an inductive thematic analysis. The school setting, language matters, the multilingual students, and the personal motivations to act in multilingual classrooms proved to influence her experience of teaching. Her approach of language as a resource in teaching in this context was enhanced or suppressed by the schools' policy and its agents. Her personal motivation, her linguistic experiences, and the nature of mathematical symbols and representations come to counterweight the influence of external factors in her teaching.

Introduction

Language diversity characterises many mathematics classrooms, and researchers from different countries all over the world have shown attention to the specific context (Barwell, Wessel & Parra, 2019). Research in mathematics education has studied both learning and teaching mathematics in language diverse classrooms. Moschkovich (2002) supports a socio-situated approach for bilingual students learning mathematics, which focuses on different resources students use when communicating mathematically and may help teachers to build on those during instruction. At the micro-level of mathematics classrooms, the teachers' role in relation to multilingual students and classrooms is observed. Cases of bilingual teachers have been studied regarding the way they teach, and positive effects on bilingual students' participation have been observed (Adler, 2001; Norén, 2008; Delacour, 2020). Nevertheless, conflicting situations teachers face when teaching in multilingual classrooms have been noticed in different contexts. Specifically, bilingual teachers teaching native bilingual students in South Africa faced teaching dilemmas such as transparency, code-switching, and mediation dilemmas (Adler, 2001). In a different context of teaching bilingual immigrant students, the bilingual teachers were hesitant to use a language other than the official language of instruction, as pointed out by Norén (2008).

The appearance of the dilemmas is mainly evidence of teachers' intentions to include all students in the teaching practice, according to Barwell, Moschkovich & Setati (2017).

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Nevertheless, tensions and dilemmas teachers are facing, are not completely personal but are connected to opposing circuit of cultures (Chronaki & Planas, 2018). Thus, Chronaki & Planas (2018) mentioned that teachers are not the only ones creating the classroom reality, but also the policies and educational programs with different views on language diversity have a significant role in that. Additionally, municipal and school policy regarding students with different language backgrounds than the language of instruction affects the way that school masters and teachers provide support for those students (Valero, 2007).

In the micro-level of the multilingual classroom, it has been observed that teachers can not only draw on their own and the students' similar learning experiences (Norén, 2008) but also have a great understanding of parents' concerns regarding their children's success in society (Delacour, 2020). Moreover, the fact that teachers have similar backgrounds and common native languages with some students influences the way they help them familiarise themselves with and learn the language of instruction to promote mathematical knowledge or communication (e.g., Norén, 2008, Delacour, 2020). The official language of instruction seems to be a key component contributing to teachers' practice in multilingual classrooms. The excluding discourse of the official language of instruction use only might be a factor to teachers' fear of using their native language in the classroom (Norén, 2008). Moreover, the unwillingness of students to use the official language of instruction contributes to teachers' dilemmas in a multilingual context (Adler, 2001). Giving attention to bilingual teachers, especially immigrants, may face additional difficulties as they might not be prepared for the cultural differences occurring in the work environment (Seah, 2014).

Following the research of the complexity of teaching in language diverse classrooms, the present project aims to study the experience of teaching in multilingual mathematics classrooms of a bilingual mathematics teacher, through her narratives regarding teaching in the United Kingdom and Greece. We address the question of which factors influence a bilingual mathematics teacher's experience of teaching in multilingual classrooms?

Conceptual background

Language in the mathematics teaching and learning in the context of language diverse classroom follows two interconnected social and political approaches that are represented in different metaphors. Looking at a social approach, the sociolinguistic perspective on language stresses the social nature of language, starting from the assumption that language is not only a cognitive but also a cultural and social phenomenon. The current study draws on Valdes-Fallis's (1978) view on bilingualism through the participation of linguistic communities that have linguistic norms. In that way, bilingualism is described not only as an individual but also as a social and cultural phenomenon involving participation in language practices of communities (Barwell et al., 2017, p. 9). Moreover, the idea of *language-as-resource* for teaching and learning mathematics has been advocated for many years in research, as an idea to move away from and challenge the deficit model of the official language of instruction use only (Moschkovich, 2002; Norén, 2008; Planas & Civil, 2013). The idea of *language-as-resource*, advocates for the potential for thinking and doing specifically

learning and teaching mathematics (Planas & Civil, 2013, p. 363). Similarly, Planas & Setati-Phakeng (2014), describe the same metaphor as the view of language as a potential resource for gaining access to particular spaces and sorts of capital. Language as a resource in practice refers to a combination of strategies, norms and process that seek to promote balanced integration of language and mathematics (Planas & Setati-Phakeng, 2014). A particular practice promoting *language-as-resource* stemming from the sociolinguistics tradition is code-switching. Code-switching is defined, through the sociolinguistic perspective, as the complex linguistic practice of using more languages during a communication, specifically the alternating use of two languages on the word, phrase, clause, or sentence level (Valdés & Fallis, 1978). The value of code-switching, as a source of communication by teachers and students, during the teaching process has been highlighted (Barwell et al., 2017).

Moving on to the political role of language, which is considered to be highly embedded with multilingual issues, has been stated in the macro- level of society and micro-level of classroom interaction. This role of language is located in the socio-political turn that point out the taken for granted views of thinking and acting that privilege some people and exclude others (Gutiérrez, 2013). In the micro-level of mathematics classroom language-as-political relates to the processes that place languages and speakers at an inferior position (Planas & Civil, 2013). Thus, it can be viewed as a way of in or exclusion from the learning process, communication and decision-making (Setati, 2008; Planas & Civil, 2013).

Research methods

This study is an extreme case study, focusing on a bilingual secondary mathematics teacher, named Layla who immigrated in her adult life and since then she works as a bilingual at schools with high educational standards. Layla is a graduate of a Mathematics Department in Greece, with 16 years of teaching experience in secondary mathematics, 12 of which happened in multilingual classrooms. Her native language is Greek, and she has been fluent in English since a young age. During her undergraduate studies, she attended two courses about mathematics terminology in English. Layla immigrated to the United Kingdom and worked for two years in multilingual secondary education classrooms, teaching mathematics and mechanics. She had no previous experience or specialization in teaching in language diverse classrooms. Since her return to Greece, she has been teaching mathematics in multilingual classrooms.

The schools she has worked at are both private schools, with students of high economic and social status. The school in the UK is a boarding school while the school in Greece is an international school which follows the British educational system. Their students are characterized by linguistic diversity and come from a variety of cultural backgrounds. During her first year in the UK, Layla taught in classrooms with immigrant students exclusively whose native language was not English. In the second year, classrooms consisted of both immigrants and British students. Most students were from Germany, China, Japan, Bulgaria, and South Korea, while British students were in the minority. At the school in Greece, the classrooms consist mainly of Greek, Arab, Chinese, Russian, and British students with a

Greek or British cultural or/and educational background. Students are distributed among classrooms based on their performance in each course. Teachers at the school in the UK were mainly British. Teachers at the school in Greece had different cultural backgrounds and they are proficient in English or native English speakers, as are directly related to British culture either because of their nationality or their immigration experiences.

The selection of Layla was based on the researchers' prior knowledge about her teaching experience in multilingual contexts in different countries, and on the fact that she lives and works as a bilingual. Regarding ethical considerations, it is noted that the teacher and the researchers knew each other and had collaborated in the past. Layla consented to be a part of this research and to be interviewed about her experience.

The data collection includes three interviews which were conducted in two phases. In the first phase, two semi-structured interviews were conducted, the duration of each was about one and a half hours. Interviews had a narrative approach as they followed the timeline of Layla's experience of teaching in the two countries. Specifically, the first interview focused on recording her language, educational, and teaching background as well as her immigration experience in the UK, in terms of her adaptation as a teacher in multilingual classrooms. The second interview focused on her experience of teaching in multilingual classrooms at the school in Greece and the relation to her experience from the UK. In the second phase, a third interview was conducted after the first analysis of the data. The results from the first two interviews were introduced to Layla and discussed from her point of view. All interviews were conducted by distance, via a video conferencing platform during the period of COVID-19 pandemic, were videotaped, and transcribed in full.

Data analysis was conducted in three phases through an inductive thematic analysis. In the first phase, through a process of coding and categorizing the generated codes, themes in the data were recognized and described (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The themes are derived from and connected with the data and not with a code framework (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The narratives were analysed interpreting the content of the text, "what" rather than "how" was told (Riesman, 2005). In the second phase, after distancing from the data, the preliminary results from the first phase were discussed again from a social and political perspective. In the third phase, the data were analysed again with a different perspective, after a peer-critique of the data analysis which was done by a group of colleagues. The last interview was included in the analysis as well. During the data analysis, the researchers were working separately, and their results interpretation was discussed to come to a common ground in the results' themes.

Results

In the following section, we address the factors that Layla views influencing her teaching experience in multilingual classrooms at the schools in the UK and Greece. The main themes identified are *the school setting, language matters, the multilingual students, and personal motivation to act in multilingual classrooms*.

The school setting

The setting of each school seems to play an important role in Layla's experience of teaching. In the UK, Layla appeared to face some *conflicts* with the head of the mathematics department (HoD) who was the main agent of the school's policy about teaching multilingual students. In particular, she claimed that the HoD had a strict attitude towards Layla's teaching method, which she brought from her teaching experiences in Greece.

The HoD wanted to keep coming into the classroom, to see what I do, how I do it, [...] if I apply some other method. Many times, afterward he told me to do it differently, without explaining to me.

Moreover, Layla highlighted that the HoD did not allow her to use the students' native languages while teaching ("They told me that we are in the UK and we have to do everything in English."). Furthermore, the HoD had complained about the use of the teacher's native language, when she practiced basic operations, such as multiplication.

In contrast, at the school in Greece, Layla seemed to *agree* with the school's policy about teaching multilingual students and to have gained the support of the HoD for her way of teaching. Specifically, she mentioned that the HoD did not discourage the use of her or the students' native languages during the lesson and at school in general.

We take for granted that students who have the same native language will help each other, and one of them can be used as a translator. The school is open to this.

In addition, the *teachers' community* at each school had an important role in Layla's experience of teaching. On the one hand, at the school in the UK, the teachers' community did not support the use of students' native language in teaching. In that context, they claimed that students should use the language of instruction and learn in this language because they were on British territory. However, Layla disagreed with that approach for teaching multilingual students, resulting in her *opposition with the teachers' community*.

My British colleagues did not do that and many times when I asked them if they were sure their students understood, I got answers like "it does not matter, and if they do not understand now. They will spend more time in the country and they will learn". [...] I support that learning means that I am gaining knowledge and If I do not understand the language, I think that knowledge cannot be gained.

On the other hand, at the school in Greece, the teachers' community accepted language diversity and tried to establish a common communication code in order to include all the students in the learning process. This approach agrees with Layla's one, so she manages to *participate* in the community.

In a very similar way to me. They want to find communication codes too. They do not say "It does not matter; students will get used to it". They are looking for more efficient ways to integrate children into their classroom.

Furthermore, each school's policy of providing students' educational background to teachers appeared as a significant element for Layla's experience of teaching and her preparation for it. In Greece, HoD informed teachers of students' backgrounds and their possible difficulties in learning and school life, contrary to school in the UK.

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At the beginning of the school year, we have a staff meeting and we have informed on a variety of issues about our students such as how many of them do not speak English and then we go to their class [...]. So, the school has already prepared me for this, and I already know to whom I have to pay attention. [...] So, we have prior knowledge about students, their previous performance, if they face difficulties in their understanding or if they face language issues.

Language matters

Language is recognised to be an important matter for Layla when teaching in multilingual classrooms. Specifically, the *native language* of students is being recognised as a *tool* or/and an *obstacle* for her teaching. In the UK, the native language of students was used by her as a *tool* for their participation in teaching processes.

The Chinese students explained to each other and I allowed it. One of them said to me, “I understand what you are saying, can I translate it to them?”

In Greece, Layla had a common language with some of the students and found code-switching to be a way to help them with mathematics terminology. Although the *native language* played the role of a *tool*, it can also be an *obstacle*. Students who have a common native language with her may resist speaking the official language of instruction creating conflicting situations.

The school has English as the language of instruction. We must speak English. There are students who for some reasons do not want to speak English but they want to use their native language. [...] The fact that I speak Greek is sometimes an obstacle.

Moreover, the role of language when teaching in multilingual classrooms became clear when she had to teach the *terminology of the mechanics* course, which was unknown to her. That brought to the surface the matter of teaching and learning in a different language and the need for a different way of representing the terminology which was accomplished by pictures.

There are things we used in mechanics, like terminology, that I didn't even know. [...] If the student does not know what a metal bar is, how do I translate it? In which language; [...] I was making something like PowerPoint [...], every word I thought they would not know, I found it in a picture and wrote the relevant terminology.

The *way of teaching mathematics* influences Layla's experience of teaching in multilingual classrooms from the beginning of her teaching in the UK. Specifically, the *role of symbols* played an important role in finding or creating a common code with students when language seemed to be an obstacle.

When there was a barrier, I said “Fine I will forget the language and I will go to symbols”. I was trying to use only mathematical symbols.

Layla perceived teaching mathematics in multilingual classrooms the same as *teaching students with a common native language* since she began teaching in the UK. Layla appeared to practice labelling in both linguistic contexts, acting like she was introducing a new mathematical concept.

Due to the terminology of mathematics [...], I showed them a symbol and told them that this symbol is called integral. There were no big differences. It is like teaching in the third class of a high school in Greece and telling them that I will call this symbol integral.

Multilingual students

Layla mentioned that her multilingual students were an important element in her experience of teaching in the UK and Greece. Both in the UK and Greece, she seems to adjust her teaching according to students' reactions, considering students' *confirmation of non-verbal teaching practices* (e.g., the use of symbols and pictures).

My students said "It is easier when we use photos. We can understand what we are talking about. Can you use pictures every time"?

In addition, Layla noticed that the *students' opposition* to the British way of teaching encouraged her to reverse her alignment with the given teaching practice. That way, she was led to include elements in her teaching that appealed to the educational backgrounds of her multilingual students.

A student complained to me that "I do not understand. Where we found this formula.", [...] and I proved to them the formula and we ended up with the theorem. The students said to me "Finally, we got it. In Germany, we did it like this, and in the UK I do not understand anything. Can we do lessons like this every day?"

At the same time, Layla noticed that the culture of multilingual students can act as an *obstacle* when trying to approach them.

With Japanese students who did not express themselves, it was difficult to communicate. The fact that they cannot talk to their teacher because they respect his role was an obstacle.

The culture of multilingual students can act also as a *tool*, promoting cooperation between students, highlighting their common cultural elements and characteristics.

I have allowed students from China to help each other. They do it very well. The Chinese are very hardworking, in general, as a people, and when they tell you that "we will help each other", they usually do it.

Personal motivation to act in multilingual classrooms

Layla presented the willingness to act in multilingual classrooms, to meet all students' needs and provide them with opportunities for learning. Her personal *experiences of learning (in) a different language* were a key point of her teaching approach in the UK. Terminology and everyday life language were distinguishable for her.

It is different to speak a language in your daily life and use this language in teaching terminology. [...] I thought that I did not understand all the terminology even though I know English, so my students who did not know English well how they will understand it?

Learning basic mathematical skills were also recognised to be more accessible in her native language.

When you are learning mathematical skills, you are learning them in one language. I have learned the times table in Greek. I cannot do it in another language, it would take me too long to do that.

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Moreover, in Greece drawing on her *experience of teaching in a different language* she became more compassionate towards multilingual students' needs.

[Ever since teaching in the UK,] I started to understand students' needs, because we were all foreigners, without a common language code, so I had to find a way to communicate. And I brought this to Greece as well.

Her *general intentions* for students to participate and understand her teaching were highly connected with her drive to provide *equal opportunities for multilingual students*. They were also connected to her need to find or create a *common communication code* with students, to her attempt to *distinguish mathematical and language issues* to support students appropriately, and finally to her feeling of *responsibility for teaching the terminology* to students.

I thought that when I was learning a foreign language I didn't learn this terminology so the students would not know it either, so I had to do something to teach them the language, while my colleagues did not take this into consideration.

Concluding remarks

The results revealed that Layla's teaching experience was influenced by the school setting, language matters, the multilingual students, and the personal motivations to act in multilingual classrooms.

The issue of language is central to the bilingual teacher's experience. In both schools, English as the language of instruction has been established, pointing "*language-as-political*" (Planas & Civil, 2013), excluding students with a dominant language other than English from the learning process. On the contrary, Layla view on language follows a perspective of "*language-as-resource*" (Planas & Civil, 2013). Specifically, she practiced code-switching between English and Greek for students with Greek educational background and encouraged students to use their native language, resisting to the experience of "*language-as-political*" (Planas & Civil, 2013). Despite her efforts, she seemed to use native languages more as a tool for communication than a resource for her teaching, due to the schools' language policy restrictions.

Regarding the school setting, the school in the UK did not provide sufficient support and resources for teaching in multilingual classrooms, leading her to look for a variety of strategies that allowed her to act according to her personal motivations. However, school's policy in Greece differs in the flexibility of the use of her or the students' native languages. There is a stark difference between her levels of participation in the teachers' community in these schools. Bilingual teachers at the school in Greece adopting a similar approach to multilingual students learning with Layla and leading her to participate in the community and be an active member.

Following, the school's policy of teaching in multilingual classrooms and the lack of resources lead the teacher to act autonomously. In this context, she uses her personal experiences and intentions to establish inclusive mathematics teaching and to provide equal opportunities and create conditions that allow students to access mathematics knowledge.

Specifically, the teacher's experiences as a bilingual seem to encourage her to create a common code of communication and to establish a language that includes all students in the learning process. Moreover, immigration experiences (Norén, 2008; Seah, 2014) not only played a role in the teaching in the UK but also reinforced her empathy for her multilingual students which, in turn, is strengthening her approach to inclusive teaching until the present time.

The demands of the contents had a different role in her teaching. Specifically, the mechanics course, which Layla was not experienced with, lead her to reflect on her teaching strategies due to the unknown terminology for her and her students. The use of symbols, symbolic representations, and graphs as non-verbal teaching practices were encouraged by multilingual students' culture and educational background, so the teacher had adjusted her practices according to these. Thus, the relation of the school's policy on language diversity and practice is renegotiated by both students and teacher (Planas & Civil, 2013). In mathematics teaching, even though she recognised the need for additional teaching strategies in a multilingual context, her prior experience with the respective terminology and the nature of mathematics representations did not lead to a differentiation to the core organization of her teaching between multilingual and monolingual classrooms.

It is a challenge to understand the complex situations a teacher experiences and tries to handle in their teaching. These situations are created not only by the multilingual classroom setting but also by the school's policy and external factors (Chronaki & Planas, 2018).

Although this research is based exclusively on a teacher's narratives, her approach of language-as-resource is very stark and likely to have been further supported through classroom observations. The influence of institutional aspects on bilingual teachers' experiences and teacher's agency in teaching mathematics in those classrooms are issues that need to be further studied and problematised.

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